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1	A Systematic Literature Review of Machine Learning Estimation Approaches in Scrum Projects	15
2	A Systematic Literature Review on Reasons and Approaches for Accurate Effort Estimations in Agile	82
3	A systematic review of studies on use case points and expert-based estimation of software development effort	34
4	An Update on Effort Estimation in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review	73
5	Data-driven effort estimation techniques of agile user stories: a systematic literature review	11
6	Unveiling the Art of Software Testing Effort Estimation: An In-depth Study of Current Techniques and Their Analysis	13
7	Ensemble Effort Estimation: An updated and extended systematic literature review	30
8	Review and Empirical Analysis of Machine Learning-Based Software Effort Estimation	24
9	Software development effort estimation: A systematic mapping study	120
10	Evolution of Software Development Effort and Cost Estimation Techniques: Five Decades Study Using Automated Text Mining Approach	1015
11	Software Cost Estimation: A Literature Review and Current Trends	15
12	Improved Software Effort Estimation Through Machine Learning: Challenges, Applications, and Feature Importance Analysis	69
13	MODEL AND DATASET TREND IN SOFTWARE PROJECT EFFORT ESTIMATION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	26
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15	Systematic Review Study of Decision Trees based Software Development Effort Estimation	50
16	Neural Networks based Software Development Effort Estimation: A Systematic Mapping Study	80
17	Computational intelligence for estimating software development effort: a systematic mapping study	38
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